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The Consumption of Electricity from Renewable Sources in the Italian Regions

It grew by an average of 83.67% between 2004 and 2021

Istat calculates the value of electricity from renewable sources. The variable is defined as the percentage of electricity consumption covered by renewable sources out of total gross internal consumption. The indicator is obtained as the ratio between the actual gross electricity production from RES (not normalised) and the Gross Domestic Consumption of electricity (equal to the gross production of electricity gross of production from pumping contributions plus the balance of exchanges with the abroad or between regions). The data refers to the period between 2004 and 2021 in the Italian regions.

Ranking of Italian regions for electricity consumption from renewable sources. Valle d'Aosta is in first place for the value of electricity consumption from renewable sources with a value equal to 255.10 units, followed by Trentino Alto Adige with a value equal to 144.70 units, and by Basilicata with a value equal to 111.50 units. In the middle of the table we find Tuscany with a value of 41.30 units, followed by Sardinia with a value of 39 units and Piedmont with a value of 36.90 units. Emilia Romagna closes the ranking with a value of 20.50 units, followed by Lazio with a value of 16.00 units and Liguria with a value of 7.30 units.

Ranking of Italian regions by percentage change in electricity consumption from renewable sources. Sicily is in first place for the value of electricity consumption from renewable sources with a value equal to 17667.67% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 1.5 units up to a value of 28 units. Puglia follows with a value of 1317.95% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.9 units up to a value of 55.3 units. In third place Sardinia with a variation equal to an amount of 828.57% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.2 units up to a value of 39 units. In the middle of the ranking there is Calabria with a value equal to 182.55% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 27.5 units up to a value of 77.7 units. Lazio follows with a value equal to +158.06% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.2 units up to a value of 16 units. Below is Veneto with a variation equal to an amount of 115.45% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 12.3 units up to a value of 26.5 units. In the last places is Tuscany with a value equal to +44.41% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 28.6 units up to a value of 41.3 units. Trentino Alto Adige follows with a value equal to +12.08% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 129.1 units up to a value of 144.7 units. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a percentage growth of +5.33% corresponding to a change from an amount of 242.2 units up to a value of 255.1 units. From a quantitative point of view, the consumption of renewable energy grew on average by 83.67%, going from an amount of 31.26 units up to a value of 57.41 units.

The consumption of electricity from renewable sources in the Italian macro-regions. We can note that the value of electricity consumption from renewable sources has grown in all Italian macro-

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regions. In particular, the value of electricity consumption from renewable sources in Northern Italy grew by 69.15%, going from an amount in 2004 to a value of 31.8 units in 2021. In Central Italy this value grew by 81.66% going from 16.9 units up to 30.76 units. In the South the value of electricity consumption from renewable sources grew from an amount of 8.2 units up to a value of 47 units or a value equal to 473.17%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data highlights the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Valle d'Aosta, Trentino Alto Adige;
- Cluster 2: Veneto, Campania, Marche, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lombardy, Sardinia, Sicily, Piedmont, Emilia Romagna, Umbria, Tuscany, Puglia, Lazio, Abruzzo, Liguria, Calabria, Basilicata, Molise.

If we consider the value of the average of the clusters we see the following ordering: $C1 > C2$. That is, Valle d'Aosta and Trentino Alto Adige are in first place in terms of value of electricity consumption. The other regions have levels much lower than the C1 values. Precisely because the values of the Aosta Valley and Trentino Alto Adige are very high compared to the corresponding values of the other regions, we try to do a clustering with 18 Italian regions, i.e. excluding the outlier regions. Therefore, if we remove the outliers, namely Valle d'Aosta and Trentino Alto Adige, we can notice the following clusters:

- Cluster 1: Emilia Romagna, Sicily, Campania, Marche, Lazio, Veneto, Liguria, Lombardy, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Sardinia, Puglia;
- Cluster 2: Molise, Calabria, Basilicata;
- Cluster 3: Abruzzo, Umbria, Tuscany, Piedmont.

From the point of view of the average value we can note the following ordering of the clusters: $C2 > C3 > C1$. We can see that in this case the first cluster is composed of 3 southern regions, namely C2. This is followed by cluster 3 which presents another southern region, Abruzzo, added to the regions of the Centre-North. Finally, the third cluster, namely C1, characterized by very heterogeneous regions belonging to the various Italian macro-regions.

Conclusions. Renewable energy consumption as a percentage of total gross consumption has grown in all Italian regions and Italian macro-regions. From the point of view of the macro-regions we can note that the southern regions tend to have higher percentages of renewable energy consumption than the central-northern regions. The case of the outliers, namely Trentino Alto Adige and Valle d'Aosta, remains very particular. It is likely that in this case the reduced population will increase the value of the percentage of renewable energy consumption compared to gross energy consumption. However, the data show a significant transformation in energy consumption in the Italian regions, with an increasingly marked orientation towards renewable energy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

